

MICS

Measuring Impact of Citizen Science

Quarterly Newsletter - October 2019

Hello, MICSers!

MICS is a new project to measure the impact of citizen science, which received two million euros of funding from the European Commission. The project involves six European partners: Earthwatch [United Kingdom], Stichting IHE DELFT Institute for Water Education [Netherlands], Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale delle Alpi Orientali [Italy], Geonardo Environmental Technologies Ltd. [Hungary], the River Restoration Centre [United Kingdom] and Institutul National de Cercetare Dezvoltare pentru Geologie si Geoecologie Marina [Romania].

But people trust other people, not projects or organisations. People are real; projects and organisations are just 'social constructs', or 'imagined realities'. And trust is even more critical in the case of a project related to citizen science. Therefore, we decided to make a less-formal newsletter and for each one the editor will be a particular person from the project.

This time, the person is me – Luigi Ceccaroni – one of the authors of the project's idea and its scientific coordinator. In this newsletter, I will share with you the news of the project, related thoughts and all such stuff. You can read my full introduction to the project on the [MICS website](#).

Luigi Ceccaroni

Scientific Coordinator

New to the project? Stay informed: [subscribe to the newsletter](#)

Get Involved

A first group of users already helped us to design part of the user interface of the toolbox. Now we are opening registration to become a beta-tester for the MICS project. You'll get early access to the MICS tools and help to shape the platform and impact assessment methods. In MICS we'd like to collect the minimum possible amount of personal information. In the majority of the cases this just means "no information". In some case, it means your email address. This is the case for beta testers. If you're interested, get in touch with Stephen Parkinson <sparkinson@earthwatch.org.uk> who is helping to coordinate our beta-testers. We are onboarding users in groups rather than all at once to ensure we can collect feedback and respond to any issues in a controlled way. Thanks for your patience. You can also invite more colleagues to try out the tools anytime!

Project update

In July 2019, the MICS project team gathered in Romania for our second plenary partner meeting. It was a great opportunity to bring all the partners together in the same room, a luxury when we spend the rest of our time working in five different countries. We were also joined for a day by four members of our advisory board who gave some really great suggestions. We spent our time discussing progress in the project and preparing for the next phase, in particular planning the co-design approach for our four citizen science case-studies.

We also had a chance to visit the Carasuhat Wetland where one of these new citizen science projects will be based. The big next steps for the project are the development of the MICS online toolbox and the co-design of citizen science activities.

>> [Read more](#)

Meet the team

As Luigi explained in his introduction, this newsletter is not just about the project but also about the people who make it happen. The MICS team brings together a group from six different organisations who have a diversity of expertise and experience. While we might sometimes have different perspectives or approaches we are united in our passion for the project and citizen science and look forward to the next two years working together.

More details about

[project team](#) >>

[advisory board](#) >>

Co-design flyer

We've created a flyer to outline the MICS approach to co-design and describe the four MICS case study sites. You can find the flyer along with other resources on the [MICS](#)

[website.](#)

Distretto delle Alpi Orientali

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant Agreement n. 824711.

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